

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL TO

**COMPUTATIONAL AND WATER ELECTROLYSIS STUDY OF
5,10,15,20-TETRAKIS(3-HYDROXYPHENYL)-PORPHYRIN**

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EQUATIONS

Electronegativity (χ) is calculated with Equation (S1) and is defined as the degree to which a molecule is able to attract electrons towards itself [1,2].

$$\chi = -\frac{E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}}}{2} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where E_{HOMO} is the HOMO energy (eV) and E_{LUMO} is the LUMO energy (eV).

The electronic potential (μ) denotes the charge transfer within a system from the ground state and is calculated with Equation (S2) [1,2].

$$\mu = \frac{E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}}}{2} \quad (\text{S2})$$

Chemical hardness (η) can be regarded as the molecule's capacity to resist the transfer of electron density from its surroundings and is determined using Equation (S3) [1,2].

$$\eta = \frac{E_{\text{HOMO}} - E_{\text{LUMO}}}{2} \quad (\text{S3})$$

Electrophilicity (ω) is defined as the decrease in energy that occurs when electrons are transferred from the donor to the acceptor in a molecules. It can be considered a measure of the favorable change in energy that occurs when a chemical system attains saturation through the addition of electrons [1,2], and can be calculated with Equation (S4).

$$\omega = \mu^2 / 2\eta \quad (\text{S4})$$

Polarizability (α), the anisotropy of the polarizability ($\Delta\alpha$), and the mean first polarizability (β), were calculated with Equations (S5) - (S7) [1]. The determined values are shown in Tables S4 and S5. The x, y, and z components were obtained using the Gaussian 03 program.

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{3}(\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy} + \alpha_{zz}) \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\Delta\alpha = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}[(\alpha_{xx} - \alpha_{yy})^2 + (\alpha_{yy} - \alpha_{zz})^2 + (\alpha_{zz} - \alpha_{xx})^2 + 6\alpha_{xz}^2 + 6\alpha_{xy}^2 + 6\alpha_{yz}^2]^{1/2} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$\beta = \left[(\beta_{xxx} + \beta_{yyy} + \beta_{zzz})^2 + (\beta_{yyy} + \beta_{yzz} + \beta_{yxx})^2 + (\beta_{zzz} + \beta_{zxx} + \beta_{zyy})^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (\text{S7})$$

The capacitive current density (i_{dl}) and the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) parameters were calculated with Equations (S8) and (S9) [3,4].

$$i_{dl} = \frac{\Delta i}{2} = \frac{i_a - i_c}{2} \quad (\text{S8})$$

Where i_{dl} is the capacitive current density (A/cm^2); Δi is the difference between i_a and i_c (A/cm^2) and i_a and i_c are the absolute values of the anodic and cathodic current densities corresponding to a given ν value, at an E value where there are only double-layer adsorption and desorption characteristics (A/cm^2).

$$\text{ECSA} = \frac{C_{dl} \times S_{\text{geom}}}{C_s} \quad (\text{S9})$$

Where ECSA is the electrochemically active surface area (cm^2); C_{dl} is the electric double-layer capacitance (F/cm^2); S_{geom} is the geometric surface of the electrode (cm^2) and C_s is the specific capacitance of a smooth electrode surface, having the value of $60 \mu F/cm^2$ [5].

The Tafel equation is presented in Equation (S11) [6].

$$\eta = b \times \log(i) + a \quad (\text{S10})$$

Where η is the overpotential (V); b is the Tafel slope (V/dec); i is the current density (mA/cm^2) and a is the exchange current density.

ECSA ESTIMATION FOR THE Gr_{P1-CB} ELECTRODE

The value of the ECSA parameter was estimated by going through the following steps:

- cyclic voltammetry experiments were conducted in a 0.1 M KCl solution at increasing scan rate values ($\nu = 10, 20, 30, 40,$ and 50 mV/s) within an electrochemical potential interval with no Faradaic currents (Figure S8a).
- the cyclic voltammetry data was used together with Equation (S8) to calculate the i_{dl} values and to obtain the $i_{dl}-\nu$ curve (Figure S8b).
- the C_{dl} value was the absolute value of the slope obtained for the $i_{dl}-\nu$ linear dependence. $C_{dl} = 5.93 \text{ mF}/\text{cm}^2$ ($R^2 = 0.9887$).
- the ECSA value was calculated using Equation (S9). $\text{ECSA} = 27.67 \text{ cm}^2$.

COMPUTATIONAL DATA

Figure S1. Optimized structure of 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(3-hydroxyphenyl)-porphyrin in the gas phase, using HF/STO level of theory.

Selected bond lengths obtained from the optimized geometry are listed in Table S1. The calculated values within the porphyrin ring are consistent with those of typical single and double bonds and are indicative of an extended delocalized π -conjugated system. In addition, the $\text{C}_{12}-\text{C}_{43}$ bond connecting the

porphyrin ring to the benzene is shorter than a conventional C–C single bond, indicating the presence of a double-bond character. The bond angle values obtained from the optimized geometry are summarized in Table S1 as well, and are comparable to those reported by Sakr and Saad [7] for 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin at the M06-2X/6-311G(d) level ($\angle C_5, N_4, C_3 = 105.43$; $\angle C_3, C_6, C_7 = 125.01$; $\angle C_7, N_{11}, C_{10} = 110.56$). The value of 71.35, obtained for the dihedral angle between the 3-hydroxyphenyl moiety and the porphyrin ring, suggests that the molecule is not planar.

Table S1. Selected optimized structural parameters (bond length, bond angle, and dihedral angle) using HF/STO level of theory, according to the labeling in Figure S1.

Bond length		Bond angle		Dihedral angle	
C ₆ – C ₇	1.47	C ₅ – N ₄ – C ₃	104.79	C ₅ – N ₄ – C ₃ – C ₆	179.28
C ₁ – C ₃	1.48	C ₃ – C ₆ – C ₇	126.04	C ₁₂ – C ₁₃ – N ₁₄ – C ₁₅	-179.30
C ₁₂ – C ₄₃	1.52	C ₇ – N ₁₁ – C ₁₀	109.36	C ₁₉ – N ₂₃ – C ₂₂ – C ₁₅	177.83
C ₁₆ – C ₁₇	1.32	C ₁₃ – N ₁₄ – C ₁₅	104.78	C ₂₄ – C ₅ – N ₄ – C ₃	-179.54
C ₂₂ – C ₂₄	1.34	C ₁₉ – N ₂₃ – C ₂₂	111.37	C ₁₀ – C ₁₂ – C ₄₃ – C ₄₄	109.43
C ₂₆ – C ₂₇	1.39	C ₁₃ – C ₁₅ – C ₁₇	107.27	C ₁₅ – C ₁₈ – C ₂₅ – C ₂₆	-111.72
C ₅ – N ₄	1.32	C ₁₈ – C ₂₅ – C ₃₀	120.10	C ₃₈ – C ₃₇ – C ₆ – C ₇	71.35
C ₇ – N ₁₁	1.39	C ₂₄ – C ₃₁ – C ₃₆	120.12		
C ₂₉ – O ₇₄	1.40	C ₃₀ – C ₂₉ – C ₂₈	119.86		

Table S2. Natural charge, population, and electronic configuration for 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(3-hydroxyphenyl)-porphyrin using HF/STO level of theory.

Atom	Natural charge	Natural population			Total	Natural electron configuration
		Core	Valence	Rydberg		
C1	-0.05025	1.99983	4.05042	0.00000	6.05025	[core]2S ^(1.09) 2p ^(2.96)
C3	0.04967	1.99982	3.95051	0.00000	5.95033	[core]2S ^(1.08) 2p ^(2.87)
C5	0.13804	1.99993	3.86202	0.00000	5.86196	[core]2S ^(1.09) 2p ^(2.77)
C6	0.04374	1.99983	3.95642	0.00000	5.95626	[core]2S ^(1.09) 2p ^(2.86)
C7	0.09752	1.99985	3.90263	0.00000	5.90248	[core]2S ^(1.05) 2p ^(2.85)
C10	0.09811	1.99985	3.90204	0.00000	5.90189	[core]2S ^(1.05) 2p ^(2.85)
C37	0.03524	1.99986	3.96489	0.00000	5.96476	[core]2S ^(1.08) 2p ^(2.89)
C40	-0.08792	1.99994	4.08799	0.00000	6.08792	[core]2S ^(1.07) 2p ^(3.01)
C41	0.18588	1.99974	3.81438	0.00000	5.81412	[core]2S ^(1.06) 2p ^(2.75)
C42	-0.11480	1.99993	4.11487	0.00000	6.11480	[core]2S ^(1.08) 2p ^(3.04)
N4	-0.30239	1.99994	5.30245	0.00000	7.30239	[core]2S ^(1.60) 2p ^(3.70)
N11	-0.26394	1.99998	5.26396	0.00000	7.26394	[core]2S ^(1.34) 2p ^(3.93)
O68	-0.29483	2.00000	6.29484	0.00000	8.29483	[core]2S ^(1.75) 2p ^(4.54)
H53	0.25899	0.00000	0.74101	0.00000	0.74101	1S ^(0.74)
H67	0.04803	0.00000	0.95197	0.00000	0.95197	1S ^(0.95)
H79	0.21181	0.00000	0.78819	0.00000	0.78819	1S ^(0.79)

Figure S2. Graphical representation of HOMO-1, HOMO, LUMO, and LUMO+1 molecular orbitals using B3LYP/6-31G(d) and B3PW91/6-31G(d) levels of theory.

The HOMO and LUMO orbitals are key contributors to charge-transfer processes, where the HOMO acts as the electron donor and the LUMO as the electron acceptor. The HOMO–LUMO energy gap is considered a critical kinetic stability index affecting the nonlinear optical response [8–10]. The corresponding HOMO and LUMO energies, as well as the HOMO–LUMO gap, are summarized in Table S3. Sakr and Saad [7] obtained similar results for 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin using M06–2X/6–311G(d).

The global chemical reactivity parameters were determined with the HOMO and LUMO orbital energies, based on Koopmans' theorem [1,11,12] and using Equations (S1) - (S4). The results are shown in Table S3. The values obtained for the 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(3-hydroxyphenyl)porphyrin are higher than those obtained by Sakr and Saad for the 5,10,15,20-tetraphenylporphyrin [7]. The OH⁻ groups are probably responsible for the increased electronegativity of the molecule being studied, leading to notable asymmetry in electronic charge distribution. In turn, this enhances the molecule's reactivity and facilitates the attraction of electrons from other compounds.

Table S3. Dipole moment (Deby), calculated HOMO (eV), LUMO (eV), energy gap (eV) and global reactivity descriptors - electronic potential (μ), electronegativity (χ), chemical hardness (η), and electrophilicity (ω) using DFT.

	Dipole moment	E _{HOMO}	E _{LUMO}	E _{gap}	μ	χ	η	ω
B3LYP/6-31G(d)	0.51	-5.21	-2.26	2.95	-3.74	3.74	1.48	6.98
B3PW91/6-31G(d)	0.53	-5.32	-2.38	2.94	-3.85	3.85	1.47	7.41

Figure S3. Electrostatic potential maps for 5,10,15,20-tetrakis(3-hydroxyphenyl)-porphyrin using DFT. (a) using the B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. (b) using the B3PW91/6-31G(d) level of theory.

In Figure S3, areas exhibiting negative potential are indicated in red and yellow, while areas exhibiting positive potential are denoted in blue.

Polarizability, the anisotropy of the polarizability, and the first polarizability were calculated using Equations (S5) - (S7) [1], and the determined values are presented in Tables S4 and S5. The calculated values from the two tables were converted to electrostatic units (esu) from atomic units (au): for polarizability $1 \text{ au} = 0.1482 \times 10^{-24} \text{ esu}$ and for hyperpolarizability $1 \text{ au} = 8.6393 \times 10^{-33} \text{ esu}$ [1]. The polarizability and the first hyperpolarizability of molecular systems are related to the efficiency of electronic communication between donor and acceptor groups associated with intramolecular charge transfer.

Table S4. The polarizability (α), anisotropy of polarizability ($\Delta\alpha$), and their elements using DFT.

	α_{xx}	α_{yy}	α_{zz}	α_{xy}	α_{xz}	α_{yz}	α	$\Delta\alpha$
B3LYP/6-31G(d)	777.66	-0.50	769.32	11.40	18.65	322.34	7.63×10^{-23}	23.08×10^{-23}
B3PW91/6-31G(d)	777.60	-0.49	768.92	11.26	18.45	322.41	7.63×10^{-23}	23.08×10^{-23}

Table S5. The first hyperpolarizability (β) and its elements using DFT.

	β_{xxx}	β_{xyx}	β_{xxz}	β_{xyy}	β_{yyy}	β_{yyz}	β_{xzz}	β_{yzz}	β_{zzz}
B3LYP/ 6-31G(d)	67.48	-159.37	-41.43	1084.64	-282.53	72.86	-28.72	26.93	-28.78
								$\beta = 103.46 \times 10^{-31}$	
B3PW91/ 6-31G(d)	66.89	-144.40	-48.38	1083.20	-284.16	72.12	-34.23	26.26	-24.94
								$\beta = 102.47 \times 10^{-31}$	

ELECTROCHEMISTRY DATA

Figure S4. Anodic polarization curves recorded on GC_0 and on (a) $GC_{P1-EtOH-1}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-1}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-1}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-1}$; (b) $GC_{P1-EtOH-2}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-2}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-2}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-2}$ and (c) $GC_{P1-EtOH-3}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-3}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-3}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-3}$. Electrolyte solution: 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . $v = 5$ mV/s.

Figure S5. Cathodic polarization curves recorded on GC_0 and on (a) $GC_{P1-EtOH-1}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-1}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-1}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-1}$; (b) $GC_{P1-EtOH-2}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-2}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-2}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-2}$ and (c) $GC_{P1-EtOH-3}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-3}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-3}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-3}$. Electrolyte solution: 0.1 M H_2SO_4 . $v = 5$ mV/s.

Figure S6. Cathodic polarization curves recorded on GC_0 and on (a) $GC_{P1-EtOH-1}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-1}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-1}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-1}$; (b) $GC_{P1-EtOH-2}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-2}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-2}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-2}$ and (c) $GC_{P1-EtOH-3}$, $GC_{P1-PhCN-3}$, $GC_{P1-DMF-3}$ and $GC_{P1-DMSO-3}$. Electrolyte solution: 0.1 M KCl . $v = 5$ mV/s.

Figure S7. (a) Anodic polarization curves recorded on GC₀, GC_{CB}, GC_{P1} and GC_{P1-CB} in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte solution, at $v = 5$ mV/s. (b) Cathodic polarization curves recorded on GC₀, GC_{CB}, GC_{P1} and GC_{P1-CB} in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte solution, at $v = 5$ mV/s. (c) Cathodic polarization curves recorded on GC₀, GC_{CB}, GC_{P1} and GC_{P1-CB} in 0.1 M KCl electrolyte solution, at $v = 5$ mV/s.

Figure S8. (a) Cyclic voltammograms recorded on Gr_{P1-CB}, in the 0 to 400 mV potential range vs. Ag/AgCl(sat. KCl), at increasing v values (10, 20, 30, 40, and 50 mV/s). Electrolyte solution: 0.1 M KCl. (b) The i_d - v graphical representation for Gr_{P1-CB} in 0.1 M KCl solution.

Figure S9. Raman spectra recorded on Gr_{P1-CB} before the anodic stability experiment performed in 0.1 M KCl solution (Gr_{P1-CB} a) and after the experiment (Gr_{P1-CB} b).

STATISTICAL DATA

Table S6. Results of the correlation analysis between η_{OER} and pH and between η_{OER} and solvent polarity.

Variable 1	Variable 2	N	Correlation	P-Value
Overpotential	pH	13	0.628	0.022
	Solvent polarity	13	-0.058	0.851

Table S7. Results of the correlation analysis between η_{HER} and pH and between η_{HER} and solvent polarity.

Variable 1	Variable 2	N	Correlation	P-Value
Overpotential	pH	12	-0.620	0.032
	Solvent polarity	12	0.602	0.012

Figure S10. (a) Heat map showing the η_{OER} values calculated for GC_0 and the porphyrin-based electrodes manufactured using the first modification strategy, at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, in $0.1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution. (b) Heat map showing the η_{HER} values calculated for GC_0 and the porphyrin-based electrodes manufactured using the first modification strategy, at $i = -1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, in $0.1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution.

Figure S11. (a) Heat map showing the η_{OER} values calculated for GC_0 and the porphyrin-based electrodes manufactured using the first modification strategy, at $i = 1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, in 0.1 M KCl solution. (b) Heat map showing the η_{HER} values calculated for GC_0 and the porphyrin-based electrodes manufactured using the first modification strategy, at $i = -1 \text{ mA/cm}^2$, in 0.1 M KCl solution.

Figure S12. (a) Heat map showing the η_{OER} values calculated for GC_0 , GC_{CB} , GC_{P1} , $\text{GC}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, Gr_0 , Gr_{P1} , and $\text{Gr}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, at $i = 5 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and 10 mA/cm^2 , in $0.1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution. (b) Heat map showing the η_{HER} values calculated for GC_0 , GC_{CB} , GC_{P1} , and $\text{GC}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, at $i = -5 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and -10 mA/cm^2 , in $0.1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution.

Figure S13. (a) Heat map showing the η_{OER} values calculated for GC_0 , GC_{CB} , GC_{P1} , $\text{GC}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, Gr_0 , Gr_{P1} , and $\text{Gr}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, at $i = 5 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and 10 mA/cm^2 , in 0.1 M KCl solution. (b) Heat map showing the η_{HER} values calculated for GC_0 , GC_{CB} , GC_{P1} , and $\text{GC}_{\text{P1-CB}}$, at $i = -5 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and -10 mA/cm^2 , in 0.1 M KCl solution.

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